

The Influence of Generational Cohort, Digital Financial Literacy and Consulting Services on Cryptocurrency Investment Intentions in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: This paper explores the predictors of the cryptocurrency investment intentions of individual investors in Vietnam, and it will focus on three main groups of factors, including digital financial literacy, generational differences, and financial advisory services. Based on 674 observations, quantitative analysis methods were used to validate the research model. The results show that digital financial literacy and access to advisory services have a positive impact on investment intentions. Both Millennials and Gen Z, simultaneously, are more proactive in accessing technology and decision-making. The problem of overconfidence had a significant effect, conversely, risk perception and herd behavior were not statistically significant. From then on, the study proposes a few implications to promote the transparent and sustainable development of the cryptocurrency market in Vietnam.

KEYWORDS: Cryptocurrency, Investment Intent, Generational cohort theory, Digital financial literacy, Consulting services.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of financial technology (FinTech) and blockchain technology has led to the emergence of cryptocurrencies as an alternative asset class with more mature market capabilities. This asset class attracts strong interest from both institutional and individual investors. In the United States, the cryptocurrency market was valued at \$1.19 billion in 2022, and researchers predict that it will grow at an average rate of approximately 12% per year through 2030 (Grand View Research, 2023). Cryptocurrencies offer the potential for significant returns, but they are also an extremely risky investment formula with the potential for rapid and constant price fluctuations (Giang, 2026).

In Vietnam, there is currently no official legal framework for cryptocurrencies and digital assets. However, participation in this market continues to increase rapidly. In 2023, Vietnam ranked second globally in the rate of digital asset ownership with over 21 million users. Furthermore, the returns achieved by investors have also increased significantly. Chainalysis (2024) reported that Vietnam ranked third globally in cryptocurrency investment returns, reaching approximately US\$1.18 billion in 2023 (Chainalysis Team, 2024). This growth, in the context of a still-developing legal framework, raises noteworthy questions about the motivations and financial decision-making processes of individual investors.

In fact, psychological and behavioral factors of investors greatly influence investment decisions in the cryptocurrency market. According to Arias-Oliva et al., expectations of return influenced by the social environment, level of financial literacy, and familiarity with technology often play a significant role in forming investment intentions (Arias-Oliva et al., 2019). However, in Vietnam, current research on behavioral finance still mainly focuses on investor psychology in traditional markets, especially the stock market (Vo et al., 2020; Toan et al., 2022). Given the rapidly changing market and volatile investor sentiment, in-depth research on cryptocurrency investment intentions remains quite limited.

This study was conducted to fill a research gap, relevant to the practices in Vietnam, and address the following objectives: (i) to understand how financial literacy, generational differences, and digital financial advisory services influence cryptocurrency investment intentions in Vietnam; and (ii) to propose some recommendations for participants in the cryptocurrency market.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. General cohort

The theory of generations was first introduced by sociologist Mannheim in 1952 in his book "The Problem of Generations," in which he defined a generation as a group of people born at the same age, who experienced significant historical events together, and who share similar perceptions and behaviors (Mannheim, 1952). This theory provides an important perspective on society, based on historical and social context to explain the behavior and perceptions of a specific age group.

In 1991, Strauss and Howe's theory expanded the concept of generations, emphasizing that differences between generations also lie in how they construct their thinking, behave when faced with risks, and their level of acceptance of socio-historical changes (Strauss & Howe, 1991). Generations are categorized by year of birth: Baby Boomers (1946–1964), followed by generation X (1965–1980), generation Y (1981–1996), and the more recent generation Z (1997–2012) (Strauss & Howe, 2000).

Typical generational differences in participation in financial markets are explained by the development of digital technology and improved financial literacy. Older generations, particularly those born before 1965 and generation X, tend to be hesitant to invest in non-traditional assets and therefore prefer familiar financial markets such as real estate (Krause, 2024). Consequently, they carefully consider their investment decisions in newer asset classes such as cryptocurrencies. Generations Y and Z, educated during the internet and high-tech boom, demonstrate better technological adaptability and higher risk tolerance than previous generations (Krause, 2024). They view new assets like cryptocurrencies as opportunities to learn about investing and diversify their portfolios (Krause, 2024).

Besides the advantages brought about by the rapid development of technology, it also carries inherent risks affecting investor perceptions and behavior (Juwita et al., 2022). Empirical studies conducted in 2022 and 2024 by Juwita and Krause show that the combination of technological skills and financial knowledge can lead to young investors becoming overconfident in their ability to assess financial markets and believing that their decisions will be successful. Therefore, they overlooked potential risks and misunderstood the link between technological skills and market control (Juwita et al., 2022; Krause, 2024).

Through broader research and definition, the generation is viewed not only as a demographic factor but also as a distinct set of financial behaviors, perceptions, and psychological patterns. Analyzing the impact of this factor not only highlights age differences but also their interaction with financial culture, thereby providing a better understanding of the motivations and barriers to investment decision-making for each group.

B. Digital financial literacy

Morgan et al. (2019) used numerous elements of literacy in DFL, for instance, multidimensional concepts to represent traditional financial literacy, capacity, and the use of digital technology (Morgan et al., 2019). As financial technology continues to develop, an essential competency has emerged which in this case is referred to as DFL, which stands for Digital Financial Literacy, to allow individuals to manage their modern finances such as digital banking, e-wallet, and online investment platform (Mishra et al., 2024). DFL comprises two components. First is financial literacy manifested in the ability of people to understand basic financial concepts like managing an asset, diversification of investment, assessment of risk and return etc. People who are financially literate tend to be able to make good investment choices and manage their finances better (Jones et al., 2024). Second, digital literacy, which reflects the ability to use digital financial tools such as blockchain, e-wallets, and online trading platforms, and includes information assessment skills and personal data security (OECD, 2024; Park, 2011).

In the context of cryptocurrency investments, which are highly volatile and heavily dependent on technology platforms, DFL is particularly important. According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), attitude and individual perception are factors that influence human intention and behavior (Ajzen, 1991). When individuals have a high level of DFL, they tend to have a more positive attitude towards cryptocurrency investment. Furthermore, the Social Learning Theory suggests that human behavior is influenced by herd mentality, arising from the process of observing the environment and society (Bandura, 1977). However, DFL can reduce dependence on herd mentality, meaning that investors have sufficient knowledge to self-analyze and make independent decisions without relying on external factors (Handoko et al., 2026). In addition, according to Prospect Theory, individuals often misjudge risk (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979), and DFL helps mitigate these biases by improving the ability to evaluate risks and returns, thereby helping them invest more consistently in a constantly fluctuating market.

The empirical evidence also reinforces the role of DFL in cryptocurrency investing. Fadli's research shows that DFL helps investors be more confident and less affected by price fluctuations (Fadli, 2024). The OECD affirms that high levels of DFL help individuals identify risks and use crypto assets in accordance with their risk appetite (OECD, 2025). Moreover, Kumari et al. (2024) suggests that higher DFL tests lower the level of perceived risk and it further increases investment intentions. Nonetheless, the cryptocurrency market is fraught with peculiar risks that can raise risk perception, such as volatility, liquidity risk, legality and cybersecurity risk. These can cause the intention to invest to decrease (Kumari et al., 2023). TPB theory states a high level of risk perceptions results in a negative attitude towards investment behaviour that leads toward avoidance. On the contrary, individuals tend to be involved in the market, when their risk perception is DFL controlled.

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C. Consulting services

Financial investment consulting services in digital form are the type of information, advice, and advocacy to support investment decision-making using technology tools including websites, mobile apps, and online channels to assist individual investors to gain access to professional information in the very unstable cryptocurrency market (FMIT Institute, n.d.).

The information asymmetry theory suggests that because of the difference between personal knowledge and their analytical capability and that of financial professionals, there is a need to seek advisory services to eliminate the information gap and the risk of making a decision (Mohn & Elizabeth, 2025). The Theory of Technology Adoption and Use (UTAUT) could be used to explain the acceptance and use of counseling services in the digital context. Based on this, easy accessibility, affordable prices and favourable terms are significant when encouraging users to use advisory services when making investment decisions (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

Trust is one of the key aspects of the investor-advisor relationship. Morgan and Hunt (2019) define trust as the extent of trust that one party has in the competence, honesty, and goodwill of the other party (Morgan et al., 2019). Financial advisory: Trust in an advisor assists investors to minimize uncertainty and have a more optimistic view of investment opportunities in high-risk markets like cryptocurrencies (Poole, 2017). It has also been demonstrated in empirical studies that trust in advisors is positively related to financial risk tolerance (Nguyen et al., 2016). In addition, the accessibility and frequency of use of consulting services are also important factors reflecting the level of service acceptance. UTAUT states that investors are likely to incorporate consulting services into the decision-making process when the service is available, affordable, and can be used on a regular basis. Recent studies have shown that individuals who have flexible access and use advisory services regularly have a higher probability of investing in cryptocurrencies (Brockbank et al., n.d.). Timely access to professional advice assists investors grasp opportunities in a timely manner and reduce uncertainty in the face of fluctuating markets. In addition, according to behavioral finance theory, investors do not always act completely rationally but are influenced by psychological factors such as fear of loss, risk avoidance, and uncertainty. Professional advice, in this case, plays an important role in reducing perceptual bias and improving the quality of investment decisions. According to the decision-making style theory, Scott and Bruce (1995) propose that in high-risk situations, people would prefer to consult an expert in order to make fewer errors in making decisions (Scott & Bruce, 1995). Empirical studies have also shown that the support of professional counseling increases the confidence and financial risk tolerance of individual investors (Nguyen et al., 2016). Thus, the digital financial investment consulting service is likely to positively affect the intentions of individual investors to invest in cryptocurrencies.

D. Cryptocurrency Investment Intention

Cryptocurrency is a form of digital asset operating on a blockchain platform, which is designed on a decentralized model, so it allows transactions to be carried without relying on third parties (Kaspersky, n.d.). The transactions of this asset are encrypted and stored on the blockchain system, ensuring a high level of transparency and security (Fidelity Investments, 2025). However, unlike traditional financial assets, cryptocurrencies are not guaranteed and are mainly dependent on market supply and demand (Peterson, 2025). This leads to high levels of price volatility, while increasing both profit opportunities and investment risks. Therefore, investment decisions are not only based on economic factors but also influenced by psychological and cognitive factors; therefore, platforms such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) are often used to explain cryptocurrency investment intentions

According to Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), investment intentions are determined by three main factors: attitudes toward behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). Specifically, many empirical studies show that positive attitudes towards cryptocurrencies and social influence, especially from online communities, have a strong impact on intention to enter the market (Almajali et al., 2022; Pham et al., 2024). Meanwhile, behavioral control perceptions – reflecting the level of confidence in investment capabilities and resources – have the same impact but are often not decisive in many research contexts (Pham et al., 2021).

In addition, Davis's (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) adds a technological perspective when it assumes that behavioral intent is influenced by perceived usefulness and ease of use. Specifically, the perceived usefulness is shown in investors' expectations of return, flexibility and global connectivity. Beside that, as trading platforms become more user-friendly and easier to use, barriers to entry are reduced, contributing to increased investment intentions (Janteng et al., 2024; Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018).

From this, it can be seen that cryptocurrency investment intention is influenced by many aspects: personal thinking, social factors and technology. The integration of the two platforms TPB and TAM not only helps to comprehensively explain investment behavior, but also creates a basis for considering the role of related factors, thereby clarifying the factors affecting investment intentions in the context of today's strong development of digital finance.

Based on the recommendations from prior discussions, the authors developed the following hypothesis:

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- H1a: Overconfidence has a positive impact on crypto investment intentions**
- H1b: Herd behaviour has a positive impact on crypto investment decisions**
- H2a: Digital financial knowledge has a positive impact on crypto investment intentions**
- H2b: Risk consciousness has a negative impact on crypto investment intentions**
- H3a: Trust in Advisory services has a positive impact on crypto investment intentions**
- H3b: Advisory utilization has a positive impact on cryptocurrency investment decisions.**
- H3c: Advisory influence has a positive impact on cryptocurrency investment intentions.**

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study targeted individuals living and working in Vietnam, focusing on generational groups from baby boomers to Gen Z, who have reached adulthood and are financially independent. The research team primarily collected data from subjects living in large cities, as these individuals have access to advanced technologies and possess a basic understanding of major financial instruments. The data is processed and analyzed using SmartPLS 3 software, using the partial minimum squared structure modeling (PLS-SEM) method in combination with bootstrapping techniques. This method allows the simultaneous evaluation of the measurement model and the structural model, the testing of research hypotheses, and the determination of the impact and statistical significance of independent variables on the dependent variable.

Figure X presents a proposed research model examining the determinants of investment intention (IV), measured by IV1, IV2, IV3, IV4. The model includes four independent variables: overconfidence (OC1, OC2, OC3, OC4), herd behavior (HB1, HB2, HB3), digital financial knowledge (DK1, DK2, DK3, DK4), and risk consciousness (RC1, RC2, RC3), which are hypothesized to influence investment intention (H1a–H2b). Additionally, advisory-related factors, including trust in advisory services (TR1, TR2, TR3, TR4, TR5), advisory utilization (AU1, AU2, AU3, AU4), and advisory influence (INF1, INF2, INF3, INF4), are proposed to have direct effects on investment intention (H3a–H3c).

Figure 1. Research Model

A. Variables Used in The Model

Primary data was collected through an online survey using the Google Forms tool between January and March 2026. The questionnaire uses a 5-point Likert scale to quantify the research concepts in the model. The questionnaire is built on scales that have been tested in previous studies, then translated and adapted to suit the context of the cryptocurrency market in Vietnam.

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Table I. Measurement Research Model

Symbol	Statement	Reference
Over Confidence (OC)		
OC1	I have a good understanding of online investment plans and digital financial products (such as online stocks, cryptocurrencies, e-funds, etc.)	Dash (2010); Touny & Shusha (2016); Glaser and Weber (2007)
OC2	I have the ability to plan my personal finances through digital tools and applications.	
OC3	I believe that my digital investing skills help me achieve returns that are higher than the market average	
OC4	I have enough experience to predict the trend of online investing that has the potential to be profitable.	
Herd Behavior (HB)		
HB1	I consult with friends, relatives, or financial advisors before investing.	Touny & Shusha (2016); Dash (2010); Adhikari & Poddar (2021); Juwita et al. (2022)
HB2	Influentials/inspirational people (KOLs...) influence my investment decisions	
HB3	I follow forums and social media groups before making an investment decision	
Digital Financial Knowledge (DK)		

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DK1	I understand the features of digital financial applications and e-banking services (Internet banking, e-wallets,...)	Vieira et al. (2024), Morgan et al. (2019), Rahayu, R., et al. (2022)
DK2	I am familiar with the terminology in the field of digital finance.	
DK3	I understand the forms of payment (QR, Internet Banking, E-wallets).	
DK4	I understand how popular e-wallets (Momo, ZaloPay,...) work.	
DK5	I understand the difference and how to use an ATM or credit card online.	
DK6	I have a basic understanding of cryptocurrencies (like Bitcoin, Ethereum, etc.)	
Risk Consciousness (RC)		
RC1	I am aware of the risks and know the security measures when using digital financial applications (Momo, ZaloPay, Internet banking,...).	Ravikumar et al (2022), Shen, Y., et al. (2018), Banik P. & Datta R. N. (2020), Tony, N., & Desai, K. (2020), Rahayu, R., et al. (2022), OECD (2022)
RC2	I understand the rights and mechanisms of consumer protection on digital financial platforms.	
RC3	I am aware that personal data may be exploited or used for malicious purposes.	
Trust in Advisory Services (TR)		

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TR1	I believe that the advisor is qualified to make recommendations that are suitable for my financial situation and investment goals.	Nguyen et al. (2016); J. Michael Collins (2012); (Poole, 2017)
TR2	I believe that financial advisors work transparently, honestly, and fairly in every transaction.	
TR3	Financial advisors always try to prioritize the interests of their clients over personal interests	
TR4	I feel secure using the information and advice provided by a financial advisor.	
TR5	I have a firm belief in financial advisors, even when the market is volatile or risky appears.	
Advisory Utilization (AU)		
AU1	The current fee of financial advisory services is reasonable compared to the value brought.	Qi et al., (2025); J Financ Serv Mark. (2021)
AU2	It was easy for me to find the right financial advisor for my needs.	
AU3	I regularly consult investment information and advice from various sources such as experts, social media, or online platforms.	
AU4	The procedure for registering and starting to use consulting services is simple and fast.	
Advisory Influence (INF)		

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INF1	When faced with important investment decisions, I tend to prioritize consulting with trusted sources	Scott & Bruce (1995); Qi et al., (2025); Sharma & Gupta (2011); Pearson, B. (2021)
INF2	I feel more confident in making investment decisions if there is confirmation from professional sources	
INF3	In my investment process, consulting with a financial advisor is an integral part of my investment process.	
INF4	I tend to follow the recommendations of financial advisors when investing	
Investment intention (IV)		
IV1	I'm planning to invest in crypto	Qi et al., (2025); Brockbank et al., (n.d.); Pilatin & Dilek (2023); Alomari & Abdullah (2023)
IV2	I will definitely invest in cryptocurrencies in the future	
IV3	I'm planning to invest in cryptocurrencies	
IV4	I will consider investing in cryptocurrencies if there is an opportunity in the future	

B. Sample Scale and Data Collection

The questionnaire is designed based on the scales that have been tested in the world, then translated and adjusted to suit the context of the cryptocurrency market in Vietnam, including 78 items in the questionnaire and items that measure the research models proposed in the research paper. This study uses an online survey method through Google Forms, which was conducted between January and March 2026, to collect data on factors that influence cryptocurrency investment intentions, including psychological factors, digital financial literacy and digital financial consulting services. The questionnaire designed by the research team consists of two main parts: firstly, demographic groups, intended to characterize the research sample. Secondly, a set of scales for the variables developed in the study in order to analyze the impact of these variables on investment intentions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

1) Sample collection: According to the demographic data presented in Table 2, it is clear that men show a greater interest in cryptocurrencies than women, as evidenced by 62.72% of the 684 survey participants. Regarding generational characteristics,

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those who grew up with technological development demonstrate a strong interest in the novelty and complexity of digital assets. The data reveals that generation Y represents a significant share, approximately 42%, and generation Z a third of the participants. Conversely, older generations, such as generation X and baby boomers, show less interest in cryptocurrencies. This shows the outstanding participation of adult generations in the digital environment for the cryptocurrency market. In terms of geographical area, the majority of survey participants came from major cities, of which Hanoi accounted for the highest proportion with 39.33%, followed by Ho Chi Minh city with 16.08%, and the rest were in other provinces and cities. In terms of education, the sample was of relatively high quality as the majority of participants had undergraduate (54.82%) and postgraduate (20.91%) degrees. In terms of occupational fields, participants are mainly active in fields related to economics – finance (27.34%), information technology (17.54%) and production – engineering (16.67%), showing a certain level of understanding of both finance and technology. In terms of income, the research sample was mainly distributed to the middle-income group. The group with an income of 10-15 million VND/month accounted for the highest proportion (about 30%), followed by the group under 10 million VND (about 23%) and the group from 15-20 million VND (20.47%). In addition, the higher income group of VND 20 million and above also accounts for a significant proportion, reflecting the interest in cryptocurrencies in various income segments.

Table II. Sample Scale of The Study

Criteria	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	429	62,72
Female	255	37,28
Generation		
Baby Boomers (born before 1964)	54	7,89
Gen X (1965 – 1980)	115	16,81
Gen Y / Millennials (1981 – 1996)	287	41,96
Gen Z (1997 – 2012)	228	33,33
Location		
Ho Chi Minh City	110	16,08
Ha Noi	269	39,33
Hai Phong	29	4,24
Da Nang	47	6,87
Hue	45	6,58
Can Tho	11	1,61
Other provinces/cities	173	25,29

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Academic Level		
Postgraduate	143	20,91
Bachelor's Degree	375	54,82
Associate Degree/College Diploma	87	12,72
High School Diploma	79	11,55
Field of activity		
Finance – Banking – Economic	187	27,34
Healthcare – Education	83	12,13
Manufacturing – Engineering	114	16,67
Marketing – Communication	108	15,79
Services - Tourism	67	9,80
Information Technology	120	17,54
Other fields	5	0,73
Average Monthly Income (VNĐ)		
Under 10 million VND	155	22,66
10 - 15 million VND	205	29,97
15 - 20 million VND	140	20,47
20 - 30 million VND	117	17,11
Over 30 million VND	67	9,80
Investment Status		
Currently investing	134	19,59
Researching but not yet invested	341	49,85
Not yet interested or invested	209	30,56

2) The Examination of the Measurement Model: Before analyzing the model, the study should assess the likelihood of general methodological bias. Since the data was collected using the same survey tool and at the same time, the risk of false correlations between variables is possible. As recommended by Kock (2015), the Inner VIF index is used to determine the level of CMB in the PLS-SEM model. If all Inner VIF values are less than 3.3, the model is considered to have no significant general method bias (Kock, 2015). Therefore, Inner VIF testing is a necessary step to ensure the objectivity and reliability of the data before further analysis.

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Table III. Inner VIF Index of Variables in The Model

	DK	RC	HB	OC	TO	RC	INF
Inner VIF	2.574	2.491	2.265	2.217	2.643	2.491	2.415

The results of the study's analysis showed that all variables had Inner VIF ranging from 2,217 to 2,643, and none exceeded the threshold of 3.3. This confirms that the data is not affected by the general methodological bias that arises from collecting information using the same tool or at the same time. Therefore, the estimates in the structural model can be trusted and seen as accurately reflecting the actual relationship between the variables in the study.

3) Evaluation of the measurement model: After confirming that the model does not have a problem of method bias, the next step is to evaluate the scale to ensure the observed variables actually reflect the theoretical concepts. Reliability and convergence validation include consideration of outer loading, internal reliability (Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability), and mean extraction variance (AVE). A scale is considered satisfactory when the observed variables have a load ≥ 0.7 (Hair et al., 2016), Cronbach's Alpha and CR ≥ 0.7 (Devellis, 2012), and AVE ≥ 0.5 (Hair et al., 2016). These conditions allow for confirmation that the scales have a high degree of consistency, a good interpretation of the variance of the observed variable, and actually measure the same implicit concept.

Table IV. Results of Evaluation of The Reliability and Convergence Value of The Scale

Factors	Variable observation	Outer loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Overconfidence	OC1	.810	.811	.876	.639
	OC2	.777			
	OC3	.806			
	OC4	.803			
Crowd Psychology	HB1	.796	.707	.836	.630
	HB2	.797			
	HB3	.789			
Digital financial literacy	DK1	.719	.839	.881	.553
	DK2	.795			
	DK3	.745			
	DK4	.702			
	DK5	.743			
	DK6	.755			
Risk Awareness	RC1	.826	.731	.848	.650
	RC2	.835			
	RC3	.756			
Trust in consulting services	TR1	.800	.848	.892	.623
	TR2	.781			
	TR3	.803			

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	TR4	.759			
	TR5	.802			
Access to counseling services	AU1	.776	.778	.857	.600
	AU2	.773			
	AU3	.778			
	AU4	.771			
Influence of professional advice	INF1	.782	.752	.843	.573
	INF2	.707			
	INF3	.767			
	INF4	.770			
Cryptocurrency Investment Intention	IV1	.787	.800	.869	.625
	IV2	.783			
	IV3	.783			
	IV4	.808			

Table 4 shows that all scales in the study have values exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.7. The loadings of the head-to-head measurements range from 0.702 to 0.835. This indicates that the observed variables are strongly correlated and capable of representing their respective concepts well. Thus, no variables were excluded from the model.

Regarding scale reliability, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of all variables are greater than 0.7, indicating optimal performance at the required content level. The composite reliability (Composite Reliability) of all factors exceeds 0.7. This confirms that the scales have high reliability and ensure stability throughout the research process.

Regarding convergence validity, the mean variance (AVE) of all factors is greater than 0.5. This demonstrates the ability to address observed variables that can explain over 50% of the variance of the latent factor, thereby confirming that the measurement model meets the convergent validity criterion.

The study tested discriminant validity using the Fornell–Larker criterion and the HTMT index. Accordingly, HTMT must be less than or equal to 0.9, and the square root of AVE of each scale must be greater than the correlation coefficient with other scales.

Table V. Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Differential Value Testing

	DK	TO	RC	TR	HB	OC	IV	INF
DK								
TO	0.808							
RC	0.642	0.672						
TR	0.754	0.865	0.578					
HB	0.761	0.800	0.602	0.895				
OC	0.840	0.766	0.606	0.721	0.721			
IV	0.789	0.814	0.551	0.826	0.733	0.736		
INF	0.720	0.850	0.508	0.895	0.882	0.639	0.697	

None of the pairs of factors in the model, based on test results, presented HT values above the widely accepted threshold (0.90), and all factors ranged below this value. The highest HT value of 0.895 was transitioned between two pair factors; TR-HB and TR-INF, respectively. While these figures are close to the threshold they remain intact within the acceptable range proposed by the studies linked above. Therefore, It can be said that this has a defined differentiating value in the model, guaranteeing that each factor is a different concept and there will not exist important redundancy between the scales.

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Table VI. Fornell-Larcker Differential Value Testing

	DK	TO	RC	TR	HB	OC	IV	INF
DK	0.744							
TO	0.657	0.775						
RC	0.507	0.510	0.806					
TR	0.640	0.706	0.456	0.789				
HB	0.588	0.597	0.433	0.695	0.794			
OC	0.697	0.610	0.468	0.598	0.547	0.799		
IV	0.654	0.645	0.424	0.682	0.552	0.593	0.790	
INF	0.566	0.653	0.379	0.716	0.644	0.501	0.542	0.757

Moreover, the Fornell–Larcker standard differential value testing results indicate that each factor's average mean extraction variance (AVE) square roots (the diagonal values) is greater than the correlation coefficient between it and other conceptual structures represented in the same related row and column. It further establishes that when we relate each factor to its associated variables then the degree of relationship between factor and corresponding observed variables is higher than its relation with other factors.

Together with the testing results pursuant to HTMT index, it can be confirmed the research model has fully conformed with criteria for distinguishing values, preserving the relative independence of the structures at model level.

4) Hypothesis testing: Study hypotheses are tested based on the structural model to assess how independent variables affect cryptocurrency investment intentions after scale reliability and differentiating value have been achieved. The normalized Beta coefficient, t-value, p-value and f^2 index were used to evaluate the results. The dimension and degree of influence is represented by the Beta coefficient; the t-value and p-value are used to test statistical significance; while f^2 evaluates how much each variable contributes to the R^2 of the model. These indicators provide the measure to adjudicate which of the hypotheses are supported, rejected and the degree of importance assigned by consumers to each determinant in explaining investment intentions. Therefore, the structural model enables learning about these interdependencies predicting and examining suitability of the whole one.

Table VII. Results of Effect Factors on Investment Intentions

Hypothesis path	Beta	Mean	STDEV	T-values	P-value	f Square	Result
H1a: OC -> IV	0.113	0.111	0.035	3.258	0.001	0.000	Supported
H1b: HB -> IV	0.024	0.026	0.043	0.551	0.582	0.001	Not supported
H2a: DK -> IV	0.241	0.244	0.046	5.298	0.000	0.053	Supported
H2b: RC -> IV	0.004	0.005	0.041	0.095	0.924	0.000	Not supported
H3a: AU -> IV	0.184	0.181	0.052	3.516	0.000	0.030	Supported
H3b: TR -> IV	0.328	0.322	0.056	5.880	0.000	0.081	Supported
H3c: INF -> IV	-0.023	-0.015	0.052	0.442	0.659	0.001	Not supported

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The results of the structural model analysis (Table 7) show that 4/7 hypotheses are accepted at the significance level of 5%. Specifically, confidence (OC), analyzed within investment intentions, is among the most positive yet weak impacts ($\beta = 0.113$; $p = 0.001$). The researchers examined these intentions due to their fascination with the way digital financial literacy (DK) ($\beta = 0.241$; $p < 0.001$) appears on driving decisions. The results involve a stronger and more significant impact, and the important role of knowledge reflects the study's idea of the connection between literacy and humanity. This excellent and impactful data contains various elements of influence, such as the level of access to counseling services (AU) ($\beta = 0.184$; $p < 0.001$), as well as the most influential factor, for instance, trust in digital financial services (TR) ($\beta = 0.328$; $p < 0.001$), emphasizing the central role of trust in the context of digital asset investment.

Conversely, risk perception (RC), crowd psychology (HB), and the influence of professional advisory services (INF) were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), thus rejecting their respective hypotheses, suggesting that traditional psychological factors do not play a decisive role. Meanwhile, trust (TR) and digital financial literacy (DK) were the two most important factors, followed by access to advice (AU) and finally investment confidence (OC). The f-square analysis showed that these effects were mostly moderate to small, meaning that cryptocurrency investment behavior is influenced by many factors outside of this model. In terms of fit, the results showed R-square = 0.565 and Q-square = 0.3848 (consistent predictive values). The SRMR = 0.049 (less than 0.09) also indicates that the model fits the data.

In conclusion, this study explored and analyzed the factors influencing investment intentions in cryptocurrencies. The research findings are significant as they help explain how people form beliefs when participating in the digital financial market. The results show that digital financial literacy and trust in advisory services are two crucial factors that strongly influence whether or not someone wants to invest. Furthermore, individual investment decisions are also influenced by their perception of risk or by the influence of others (herd mentality).

Figure 2 presents the SEM roadmap of the accredited research model, thereby visualizing the relationships between factors including overconfidence, crowd psychology, digital financial literacy, risk perception, access to advisory services, etc confidence in digital financial services, the influence of professional advice, and the intention to invest in cryptocurrencies.

Figure 2: Tested SEM Path Diagram

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B. DISCUSSION

The results of the study reflect changes in financial behavior under the influence of technology and generational characteristics. Specifically, factors of digital financial literacy, overconfidence, trust, and access to digital financial services have a positive effect on investment intentions, while risk perception, herd behavior, and professional advice have no significant impact. Some of the key results are as follows:

Firstly, the role of the digital financial literacy team in cryptocurrency investment intentions

The results of the analysis indicate that digital financial literacy has a positive impact on investment intentions, which is consistent with previous studies when affirming that financial technology literacy reduces uncertainty and increases market participation (Fadli, 2024; Jones et al., 2024; Kumari et al., 2023). In the context of cryptocurrencies being complex assets, knowledge becomes a necessary condition to participate in the market. Therefore, Gen Y and Gen Z will be able to use digital tools more effectively, thereby improving investment orientation (Handoko et al., 2026). In contrast to many previous results, risk perception is often seen as having a negative impact; however, this factor is not statistically significant (Sagheer et al., 2022; FINRA, n.d.). This shows that risk is no longer a barrier to investment decisions as it has been integrated as part of financial capacity. Risk is considered an inevitable factor and is actively considered by investors in their decisions.

Second, the role of psychological characteristics on cryptocurrency investment intentions

The results show that overconfidence has a positive effect on investment intentions, in line with Krause's study. This reflects the trend of quick decision-making and high risk-taking, which is common among young investors, in contrast to the cautious tendency of older generations (Krause, 2024).

However, the herd behavior factor had no significant impact, suggesting a decline in the role of the crowd effect. This is in contrast to previous studies by Touny & Shusha, 2016; and Krause, 2024; at that time, people are affected by social influences, they often tend to suffer from FOMO and follow others (Krause, 2024; Touny & Shusha, 2016). However, as the majority of investors are now highly educated and active in the field of economics and technology, they tend to make decisions more independently, based on personal analysis rather than being dominated by society

Third, the role of the advisory service team in cryptocurrency investment intentions

Research shows that trust in digital financial services is the factor that has the strongest influence on investment intentions. These results are consistent with studies by Poole (2017) and Nguyen et al. (2022) – emphasizing the key role of trust and technology platforms in the context of risky markets and lack of a mature regulatory framework (Nguyen et al., 2023; Poole, 2017). At the same time, the level of access to digital financial services also has the same impact, reflecting the role of convenience and accessibility in helping to reduce barriers to market entry (Brockbank et al., n.d.; Shaista Anwar, 2025).

Previous studies of Nguyen et al. (2016), Scott & Bruce (1995), and Shahzad et al. (2018) have often indicated that professional advice plays an important role; however, the research team's results did not show a significant impact. It means that investors, especially younger generations tend to base on informal sources to make decisions, instead of depending on the others.

V. CONCLUSION

With the development of digital technology, Vietnam is undergoing a profound technological transformation. This research confirms the impact of financial literacy, generational differences, and advisory services on the investment intentions of Vietnamese people. In line with the government's ultimate goal of establishing an optimal legal framework, current generations can be more autonomous in their financial decisions through technology and autonomy, thereby building effective investment strategies.

However, to achieve optimal results, the support of stakeholders is also crucial. Specifically, digital platforms and financial transactions need to prioritize improving the user experience. These technologies need to be designed with tool to mitigate the risk of investor data leakage, while the interface needs to be simple and intuitive to foster investor loyalty. Furthermore, raising public awareness helps people better understand the information and regulations related to cryptocurrencies. Government involvement will enhance transparency and mitigate risks by encouraging the use of cryptocurrencies, thereby creating a sustainable and secure environment.

For investors, when participating in the market, they should understand fundamental knowledge and essential financial skills to minimize the risk of fraud. Furthermore, investors should conduct their own research and develop their investment skills, rather than following trends or investing impulsively. This will help them make informed decisions and gain a better understanding of the digital asset market.

The authors' research has contributed a small part to a better understanding of investment intentions, but due to the short time and limited scope of the study, it is not possible to create definitive conclusion about the investment intentions of different

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generations. Further empirical studies are needed to address these shortcomings and to continue researching the intentions and behaviors of different target groups.

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